

pseudostems was infected and another weed, *Bracharia* sp., also was probably infected. In the Chiriqui area 200 miles west of Panama City, rice in six large rice farms did not have bacterial blight, but many colonies of the local common weed *Panicum maximum* showed blight symptoms. If isolation and inoculation experiments confirm the observed symptoms to be those of bacterial blight of rice, the original hosts of the bacterium would appear to be the weed species. Upland rice culture probably has localized the disease; in paddy rice, water is a major agent for dissemination of the bacterium. No bacterial blight was noted on rice on many farms of the Boliche and Samborondon areas of Ecuador, but *P. maximum* grew everywhere and in most places showed symptoms typical of bacterial blight. ❧

Seed-borne infection and ufra disease

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Seth observed *Ditylenchus angustus*, the nematode pathogen of ufra disease, in rice grains. Hashioka sprayed a suspension of nematodes in water onto rice seeds but the seeds did not produce diseased plants.

Studies in Burma showed that heavily infested plants produced very little seed; the panicles contained many unfilled grains. Microscopic examination showed the presence of about 15.4 nematodes in each unfilled "grain" and 5.3 in one mature grain. One mature seed carried too little inoculum to cause disease. However, large numbers of seed grown together resulted in disease when naturally infected seeds were used as the source of inoculum. ❧

Testing some pesticides against ufra disease

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Preliminary tests showed 4 of 47 pesticides were significantly better than a check spraying in increasing the rice

yield in pots infested with the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*, which causes ufra disease. The 4 pesticides were compared for effectiveness in further tests.

Ten heavily infested C4-63 rice plants, each in 1-kg soil in a 25-cm-diameter pot with 3 cm of water above the soil, were sprayed 3 times at weekly intervals with each pesticide suspension (33 ml, 0.21% ai.), or 0.07 g a.i. of carbofuran granules was sprinkled on the soil 3 times. One control was included with diseased plants and one with healthy plants. Four weeks after spraying, the average number of fertile tillers per pot for the various treatments were: healthy control, 6; diseased control, sprayed with water, 0; with monocrotophos, 1.8; with phenazine, 2.3; with parathion, 2.4; with carbofuran,

4.6. LSD at the 1% level was 1,702.

In another pot test of varied dosages of carbofuran granules (3% a.i.), the density of nematodes was determined by soaking 1-cm-long shoot sections, counting the nematodes in the soaking water, and calculating the number that would have been found in 1 g of shoot. There were 10 replications. With carbofuran applications of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 g/pot, the numbers of nematodes found were 238.9, 96.0, 84.6, 34.1, 18.4, and 17.7, respectively. L.D. 50, calculated according to Bliss, was found to be 0.9825 g granules per pot. Assuming 1 M kg to be the weight of 1 ha of soil 15 cm deep, L.D. 50 is about 1,000 kg/ha of carbofuran granules.

The pesticides may not be economical for use against ufra disease of rice. ❧

Pest management and control

INSECTS

A new lepidopterous pest of rice

Lourdes A. Malabayoc, research assistant, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

A hairy, greenish caterpillar about 20 mm long when full grown has been observed attacking rice plants. Unchecked populations can increase rapidly and cause severe defoliation (see figure). The pest was first observed in a screenhouse at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) in December 1975, and later on the IRRI farm. The same insect had been reported damaging rice plants at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in Nueva Ecija, Philippines, in September 1971, and in Pangasinan, Philippines. A. G. Hayes at the British Museum of Natural History identified specimens as near *Rivula atimeta* Swinhoe, 1905.

The adult moth is slightly larger than the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*. It is cream colored with a tinge of very light brown at the edge of the forewings. The abdomen of the female is greenish due to the presence of eggs.

Rice plants show defoliation caused by a hairy, greenish caterpillar in IRRI Screenhouse.

The eggs, very light green, are round and laid on the leaves singly or occasionally in rows. A female can lay as many as 224 eggs. Incubation lasts 4 or 5 days. The first and second of five larval instars feed mainly on the epidermis. The third instar begins eating the leaves. About 1 month is required to complete a generation.

The pest has been most severe in the

screenhouse where varieties are being screened for stem-borer resistance. However, it is common on the IRRI farm and can be considered a potentially serious pest.

Any reader with information on a similar pest should write to the Entomology Department, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Brown planthopper in Borneo

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Severe hopperburn covered about 0.2 ha in some seed-multiplication plots at a Department of Agriculture rice station in Brunei, Borneo, in early January 1976. All plants in the area were killed. Large numbers of a single species of delphacid

collected from the outbreak area were identified as *Nilaparvata lugens*.

Rice grown at the station receives fortnightly applications (14 kg/ha) of 3% granular carbofuran. Some affected plots had also been sprayed with methamidophos (Tamaron). The outbreak is the first recorded damage to rice by *N. lugens* in Brunei.

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Herbicides for direct-sown upland rice

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In 1975 kharif, nine chemicals were tested for weed control in direct-sown upland rice. The chemicals were sprayed

4 days after the direct seeding of the cultivar IET 1444. Mixed weed seeds had been uniformly broadcast at the time of land preparation.

Of the nine herbicides (see table), AC-92553 showed the best control. The trial was conducted under the auspices of the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project.

Grain yield and weed control in direct-sown upland rice, 1975 kharif, Mandya, India.^a

Herbicide	Formulation concn	Application		Weed wt (kg/15-m plot)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
		Rate (kg a.i./ha)	Time ^b		
Butralin	480 g/l	2.0	4 DS	4.0	1225
AC-92553	250 g/l	2.0	4 DS	1.2	3487
Butachlor	600 g/l	2.0	4 DS	5.9	1115
Piperophos + dimethametryn	500 g/l	2.0	4 DS	3.8	1601
Propanil	35%	3.0	18 DARE	3.4	1419
Oxadiazon	25%	1.0	4 DS	2.5	2513
Fluorodifen	30%	2.0	4 DS	2.7	0924
USB 3153	12.5%	2.0	4 DS	3.9	1662
Dinitramine	25%	2.0	4 DS	2.9	2543
Hand weeding	—	twice	20 & 40 DARE	0.6	3176
Hand weeding	—	as and when necessary		0.6	2856
Untreated control	—	—	—	6.9	1009

^aCD (0.05): 990. ^bDS = days after seeding; DARE = days after rice emergence.

soil and crop management

The use of *Azolla pinnata* as a green manure for rice

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Azolla can use atmospheric nitrogen that is fixed by symbiotic blue-green algae. Observations on the use of *Azolla pinnata* in rice culture at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, are encouraging.

The fern multiplies rapidly except during April, May, and June. Phosphorus promotes *Azolla* growth; superphosphate is a superior phosphate source. An inoculum of 0.1 to 0.4 kg/sq m increased to 0.8 to 1.5 kg/sq m of green matter in 8 to 20 days, amounting to 30 to 50 kg N/ha. Furadan (3 kg a.i./ha) effectively controls lepidopterous and dipterous insects, which damage *Azolla* severely. Pot and field experiments showed that incorporation of 8 to 10 t/ha of fresh *Azolla* before transplanting increased rice yield as much as did 30 to 40 kg nitrogen from ammonium sulfate. Inoculation of a field with *Azolla* after rice transplanting, and the incorporation of *Azolla* after its growth stimulated rice growth. However when water level was high, rice plants became entangled in the *Azolla* mat.

Tests of a tiny water fern, *Azolla*, as a source of nitrogen in rice fields, are encouraging. *Azolla* uses nitrogen fixed by the blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae*.